

AUTOMATED CONTROL SYSTEM FOR PRODUCTION PROCESSES

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Abstract

From the past to the present, a lot of research has been done in a society that is constantly in need of innovation. Thus, automated process control systems are the highest stage of complex automation and are designed to provide a significant increase in labor productivity, improve the quality of products, as well as protect the environment.

Currently, process automation is widely used in many industries and activities, from manufacturing processes to shopping in stores. Regardless of the size and scope of the organization, almost every company has automated processes.

Process automation systems, which can replace human power in any business sector, use important control systems such as robots, computers, and information technology. This ensures increased quality and flexibility in all production processes. This approach can allow full management of operations, data, information and resources through the use of computers and software that reduce the degree of human participation in the process, or completely eliminate it.

Keywords: automation, process efficiency, technological processes, efficiency, automated control systems, innovative technologies.

Industry transformation is characterized by minimization of human involvement in the production process and the transition to efficient automated control. New technologies have emerged that have transformed traditional manufacturing into digital manufacturing. At the same time, a characteristic feature of digital manufacturing is that none of the advanced manufacturing technologies, taken on its own, can provide a long-term competitive advantage. Currently, there is a need for complex systems of technological solutions that allow developing and producing competitive new generation products in the shortest possible time. It should be noted that disruptive technologies and new business models are in a sense turning traditional industries upside down, and horizontal platforms are eliminating players who are not fast enough to respond to digital changes. [1]

Today, automation of production processes is the main and important direction of production all over the world. Everything that was previously performed by man himself, his functions, not only physical, but also intellectual, are gradually moving to technology, which itself performs technological cycles and exercises control over them.

Automation of production processes allows several times to increase labor productivity, improve product quality and more rational use of production resources, increase its safety, environmental friendliness, etc. [2]

Each production process includes main and auxiliary technological processes. The main technological processes ensure the transformation of raw materials into finished products, and auxiliary technological processes ensure the release of products used to service the main production. For example, you can show the production of energy for your own needs, the preparation of production, the manufacture of tools and spare parts for the repair of enterprise equipment.

Technological processes can be distinguished by the characteristics of manufactured products, materials

used, production methods used, organizational structure, etc. But despite their distinctive features, they also have a number of characteristics that allow combining various processes into groups.

The main goal of automation of technological processes:

- reduce the number of staff;
- accelerate production, increase its volume;
- improve the overall efficiency of the company;
- improve safety, economy, environmental friendliness;
- reduce the cost of raw materials;
- increase the quality of products.

The great importance of automation of technological processes lies in the fact that within the framework of one production process it is possible to organize a production management system and an enterprise management system. The introduction of automation requires the utmost clarity in the work of all parts of the enterprise production process system.

The automatic control system replaces the control system and uses machines, electronics or computers that replace the actions of the operator. An instrument called a sensor is added that can measure the value of a parameter and convert it into a proportional signal. This signal is given to the input of a machine, electronic circuit, or computer called a controller. The controller performs the function of an operator to evaluate the measurement and issue an output signal to change the settings of the control equipment through an actuator connected to the equipment by a mechanical link. When automatic control is applied to systems that are designed to regulate the value of some variable to a predetermined value, it is called automatic process control.

We single out the following main directions for the technological installation in the development of the control system:

I. Solution of the issue of management organization. It can be local or centralized. Management of technological objects is usually centralized and carried out from operator stations.

II. Controlled parameters, which provide the most complete measurement information about the technological process, about the operation of the equipment. The main parameters of the process - temperature - are subject to control. pressure, level, etc. To assess the technical and economic performance of a process unit and perform accounting and settlement operations, it is necessary to measure the consumption and quantity of raw materials, finished products, heat carriers, etc. Where possible, it is necessary to use quality analyzers - chromatographs, gas analyzers, concentration meters, density meters, viscometers, etc., as well as analyzers of wastewater and gas emissions into the atmosphere;

III. Choice of adjustable parameters and channels for application of control measures;

IV. Selection of alarm, blocking and protection parameters. This section is developed based on the requirements for the safe operation of the process, taking into account a number of factors: process specifications, instructions for starting, maintaining and stopping the process, alarms. At the same time, methods, guidelines, norms, rules, regulations, etc., valid for various technological installations, are given.

V. Choice of means of automation. Automation tools should be selected in accordance with the decisions made on the control, monitoring and indication of process parameters and taking into account the provision of automatic protection and blocking. It is important to take into account the following basic requirements:

- devices should be selected from among those mass-produced by the instrument-making industry, that is, according to the current nomenclature reference books;

- automation equipment must meet the requirements for safe operation of their

- in terms of technical characteristics, devices and other means of automation should be selected taking into account the operating conditions: pressure, temperature, physical and chemical properties of the controlled environment.

A large number of elements are used to manage modern objects. The set of elements involved in the management is called the control complex. A typical control complex consists of elements of the following types (figure): D - awareness sensors; S - means of information transmission; L - control elements; O - controls; - k, k^1 - various converting and transitional devices

The management of a complex system can be centralized and decentralized. Centralized control involves the concentration of control functions in one center of a complex system [4]. This structure has several advantages:

- allows you to easily implement the processes of information exchange;
- creates fundamental opportunities for optimal management of the system as a whole on a global scale;
- eliminates the need to send intermediate results;
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- makes it easy to correct volatile data;
- Allows you to achieve maximum efficiency with minimal maintenance of technical means.

From a systemic point of view, the main disadvantages of a unified management structure are: the need for exceptionally large amounts of storage, high performance and reliability of data processing tools to achieve an acceptable quality of management;

a large total length of communication channels in the presence of geographically dispersed controls.

Decentralized management is the distribution of management functions among individual elements of the system. The creation of a system with such a structure is possible only if the control objects are independent in relation to material, energy and information resources. To prepare a control action on each object, only information about the state of this object is required. In fact, such a system is a collection of several independent systems that have their own information and algorithmic base.

When using a hierarchical control system, the control process is greatly simplified. Management of the hierarchical structure is characterized by the presence of several levels of management.

Conclusion

Automated process control system - a set of hardware and software tools that manage and control production and technological processes, maintain feedback

and actively influence the process when going beyond the established parameters; provides regulation and optimization of the controlled process.

When creating automated process control systems, the tasks facing control systems from monitoring individual devices and parameters to automating the process as a whole have become more complicated. The use of modern automated process control systems not only allows effective management and control in the production sector, but also helps to prevent errors by partially eliminating the influence of the human factor in management. At the same time, in order to increase the load on decision-making in the automatic control system, it is urgent to increase the autonomy of the automatic drive control system and redistribute functions. In this case, this situation includes the development of an intellectual component of an automated process control system for the formation of algorithms for responding to modes and control systems for the operation of wireless technologies, which leads to increased security requirements from unauthorized access.

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METHODS FOR ENGINEERING CALCULATION OF CHARACTERISTICS OF MATERIALS AS DRYING OBJECTS AND EFFICIENT PROCESS PLANTS PARAMETERS

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МЕТОДЫ ИНЖЕНЕРНОГО РАСЧЁТА ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК МАТЕРИАЛОВ КАК ОБЪЕКТОВ СУШКИ И ПАРАМЕТРОВ ЭФФЕКТИВНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ УСТАНОВОК

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Abstract

The necessity is shown and the possibility is proved of a systematic approach, on a scientific basis, to the problem of creating effective dryers that meet modern requirements in terms of intensity, resource saving, product quality, as well as environmental friendliness.

Аннотация

Показана необходимость и доказана возможность подходить системно, на научной основе к проблеме создания эффективных сушильных аппаратов, соответствующих современным требованиям с точки зрения интенсивности, экономии ресурсов и высокого качества продукта при обеспечении экологической чистоты.

Keywords: drying, material, dispersed, fluidized, innovations

Ключевые слова: сушка, материал, дисперсный, псевдооживленный, новации